
Intellectual Property Law's In India

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology which is known for carrying out various tasks efficiently with little or no human intervention at all. Generative AI is one of the branches of AI which is known for generating content at par with human intelligence. Generative AI tools like ChatGPT, Google's Bard and DeepAI are being used in today's world by students, academicians, employees, employers, news channels and others to create textual, pictorial or video-graphical content. All such generated content suffers from one common issue, that is, their copyright. Most of the users are unaware of copyright in the work generated by them using the generative AI tools. They do not know whether the copyright exists in AI-generated work and who is the owner or author of such copyrighted work. The article analyses the subsistence of copyright in AI-generated work and the conditions and criteria of such copyright, if any. It traces the content creation process of generative AI tools and the contractual aspects pertaining to it. Further, the article examines the issues of copyrightability of AI-generated work in various countries and compares it with the legal standing in India. Lastly, the impact of AI-generated work on the Indian copyright regime has been analysed and accordingly, suggestions have been made which may be implemented to address the plethora of challenges arising out of or in relation to AI-generated work.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Generative AI, Chat GPT, Bard, Deep AI, Copyright, Author, Owner

Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technological development in the modern world that is changing the way of carrying out work, especially in creative works. The Cambridge Dictionary defines AI as a 'computer

technology that allows something to be done in a way that is similar to the way a human would do it'.¹ However, it can take any form and can be used in various systems like smartphones and machines and in various resources like websites and software. Therefore, it is something more than just computer technology. The

reason behind its popularity and one of its main features is that AI can carry out tasks with little or no human involvement at all.² The work that humans perform and give results in hours or days, many of such work like composing lyrics of songs, writing articles, creating images, and presenting news as an anchor can be performed by AI within a blink of an eye. On account of this technological development, a distance has occurred between human creativity and artificial creativity as there is either little or no human contribution at all in AI-generated work.³ Due to the humans' distance from creativity coming out of AI, the copyright regime across the world is witnessing a common challenge in recent times. The copyright principles trace their origin in human labour on account of which the work of human creators is protected for their use only or for others' use but only with the prior permission of the human creators.⁴ Various theories emerged in the copyright domain over time, however, what remained intact is the substantial involvement of humans in the creation of work without which the copyright protection is not supposed to be granted. Copyright law has an inherent assumption that there are human creators who creatively, originally, and independently create work.

However, a threat has arisen to the aforementioned traditional and inherent assumption due to the creation of work by a non-human creator, i.e., AI. On account of the same ground, the article analyses the challenges that AI-generated work is posing to copyright law and their implications on copyright authorship and ownership because in copyright law authors are defined with respect to a particular kind of work. It also raises the question with respect to the originality of the work. This paper focuses on these two pertinent questions. Generative AI Tools

and their Work Generation Procedure AI is a technology available in various forms, viz. Software, extension, and applications, to carry out the assigned task and generate the results or work. Such software, applications and extensions are collectively referred to as AI tools which use artificial intelligence technology to perform the tasks. They are developed keeping in view the specific purposes and objectives. Therefore, the functions of AI tools differ, for instance, many AI tools carry out the function of collecting and rearranging textual and numerical data, various

Chat GPT:

AI tools like ChatGPT and Google Bards generate textual responses and other AI tools like Deep AI and Midjourney generate pictorial work. Thus, AI tools are developed keeping in view specific needs and uses in a variety of industries, ranging from education, law, finance, and healthcare to the marketing industry, to automate tasks, analyse data and enhance productivity.⁶ Among all, there is one category of AI tools called generative AI tools, which is known for its peculiar generative function. Generative AI tools are those AI-based tools the function of which is to generate responses or work as per given instructions by extracting data from its database which it has been trained upon and/or from articles, books, newspapers, and other public webpages which are available on the internet. They are trained on a massive amount of data which allows them to generate responses in simple language for questions asked to them.² Generative AI tools are being used for various purposes, viz. writing assignments and theses in academia, generating content for emails and creating images, videos, and voiceovers. For instance, a person may give a written

or oral command to a generative AI tool to “write a short note on the protection of plant varieties as intellectual property” and on receiving the command, the generative AI tool digs into its database which it has been trained upon to generate the work in the form of a short note. Similarly, a command to “draw a picture of an Indian man from 1870s” may be given to a generative AI tool which will generate the work in picture form using the database which it has been trained upon. Therefore, such AI-based tools that have been developed to generate work, either textual, pictorial or in any other form, are known as generative AI tools.

AI Tools:

It is the generative AI tools that pose challenges to copyright law because of the work generated by them. The generated work is generally literary work, artistic work or sound recordings, the ownership of which is covered within the purview of copyright law. Therefore, with every AI-generated work comes the legal aspect of its copyright protection and ownership. However, it is pertinent to note that the human role in the creation of work by generative AI tools is too limited. Humans are not required to perform any task other than giving commands to the tools for the generation of work.⁸ It is the “too-limited role” which challenges the copyright law and raises the question of whether such a “too-limited role” is enough to obtain copyright ownership in favor of humans playing the too-limited role. The question cannot be answered straightly in affirmative or negative as it can have a long-lasting impact on copyright law not just nationally but across the world because the development of law in one country ultimately reaches to and impacts other countries as well. Therefore, the issue

needs to be analyzed keeping in view the current copyright regime and future perspectives to ensure that the law remains technologically neutral, rather than being technology-specific because of the development of artificial intelligence and the increasing use and popularity of generative AI tools. Terms of Use of Generative AI Tools and Issues thereof Terms of Use of the generative AI tools are the terms and conditions laid down by the developers that provide for the rights and obligations of users, including the ownership of generated work and the extent of ownership, arising out of the use of their tools and the work generated thereto. However, there is a pertinent issue in this regard which the Authors have discussed post-coverage of Terms of Use of significant generative AI tools. Chat GPT’s Terms of Use assigns to the users all the rights, title, and interest in the generated content to the “extent permitted by applicable law”.⁹ So, users may claim rights in the generated content if the law permits and the generated content reflects the choices and creativity of the user without which the desired level of the content could not have been generated. However, the terms of services mention that if someone is infringing one’s intellectual property rights, they can send a notice to Google of the infringement and appropriate action would be taken.

Deep AI:

Deep AI’s terms of service provide that all content generated by its tools and APIs are free of copyright and users may use them for any legal purpose including commercial use. However, it further mentions that the users agree not to use any services, inter alia, in any way that violates any applicable national, federal, state, local or international law or regulation. The

impugned terms clarify that though the generated work may be copyright-free, but their AI tools are not to be used to create any work that would be volatile of any national law, inter alia, copyright law. Thus, generative AI tools have varying terms of use or service which provides for varying nature of ownership of generated work. However, a common element among all is that they have avoided vesting themselves with the ownership of work generated by their generative AI tools which means that claiming copyright in AI-generated content is dependent on various factors. It is pertinent to mention that generative AI tools have been trained on massive data available on the internet, including articles, books, newspapers, social media posts and other public web pages. In particular, ChatGPT has been trained on massive internet data available till 2021 and generates responses by using and restructuring the data which it has been trained upon.¹² Google's Bard is based on the LaMDA language model which has been trained with about 1.56 trillion words from various sources and 137 billion parameters to make it talk with the user instead of merely producing text.¹³ Further, DeepAI has been trained on a large amount of diverse text data from the internet, allowing it to learn a broad understanding of language and effectively respond to a wide range of user queries. The prominent issue in this regard is that such existing data, on which generative AI tools or their underlying language model has been trained, may be copyrighted. As a result, a work generated by generative AI tools may infringe someone's copyright if it contains or is similar to any copyrighted work.¹⁴ In view of this, the assignment of the rights in the generated responses to users as per the Terms of Use, as in the case of ChatGPT, is immaterial because neither

the tool nor its owner is the actual copyright owner, rather the actual copyright may already be existing with someone else. Similarly, work generated by DeepAI may also not be copyright-free as claimed by its Terms of Service. On the same footing, literary work generated by Google's Bard may also be someone's copyrighted work. Copyright of AI-Generated Work in India vis-à-vis Element of Originality and Roles of Various Contributors Copyright protection has historically been applicable in situations where technology has been used as a medium to assist an individual in doing a job (for example, utilising a camera to take a photograph). In these cases, the individual was recognised by being the artistic mind who defined or created the scenario resulting in the initial script. Recent developments in machine learning and the rise of computer resources have ensured that AI can now build works that are, no doubt, independent of human imagination.

Copy Right:

This raises the question of whether these AI-created works can be protected by copyright? The Copyright Act, 1957 governs the copyright regime in India. The Act grants copyright protection on literary, dramatic, musical, and artistic work, cinematograph film and sound recordings.¹⁶ AI tools can generally generate literary, musical and artistic work. However, the grant of copyright on generated work depends upon various criteria, inter alia, originality of the work and creativity on the part of an author. Originality under the Copyright Law Originality is one of the fundamental yardsticks to test the copyrightability of a work. The basic requirement of originality is that the work must originate from the Author and not be copied.¹⁷ The degree of

originality varies with the jurisdiction. The United Kingdom follows the “sweat of the brow” doctrine which prescribes that employing the skill and labour of authors is sufficient for granting copyright protection to a work.¹⁸ The United States follows the “modicum of creativity” doctrine which accepts a work to be original if it is “independently created” and has a “minimum degree of creativity”. India, till 2008, followed the “sweat of the brow” doctrine. However, the Supreme Court of India, in the

Conclusion:

Once upon a time, only humans were known for creation, invention, and innovation. As time passed, humans kept creating, inventing, and innovating, as a result of which, today they have created arguably an equivalent or advanced version of themselves in the field of creativity, known as Artificial Intelligence. AI can create, copy, replicate, carry out tasks and give results with better efficiency than humans. The accuracy of resultant work may be questionable, but it may be only a matter of time that many tasks not requiring human intervention

are going to be the responsibility of AI in future. However, the issue of copyright protection and ownership of created work and the credit for its creation are matters of ongoing debate. One section advocates for protecting AI-generated work under copyright law and vesting the users of the AI tools with authorial rights, whereas the other section opposes the above view. It is worth noting that copyright attaches to original work of authorship fixed in any tangible medium of expression, which may not even be known or may be developed later.⁵⁵ So, copyright is designed to adapt with time and human creativity is the sine qua non at the core of copyright.

References:

1. Pokhriyal A & V Gupta, Artificial intelligence generated works under Copyright Law, NLUJ Law Review ,6 (2) (2020) 116.
2. Nimmer M B, Nimmer D & Nimmer I, on Copyright 2-5 (Matthew Bender, Review edn., 1963)